

The “Average” Error of Survey Estimates

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1. Setup

The ACS estimates, among other things, PPH and vacancy rates for every county in the U.S. The question of what the “average” error of these estimates is has arisen. “Average” can take many meanings. In its most literal sense, it is the average of the unknown true values less their estimates. In the case of an unbiased estimator, this is always zero. This uninteresting result leads us to consider absolute errors. These are always nonnegative. They are interpreted as the distance between the true values and their estimates. “Average” takes on two meanings: the usual meaning as the mathematical average of a set of numbers; and the median, the value at which half of the errors lie above and half lie below. Both of these depend on the standard deviation of the estimate. Therefore, their standardized versions, divided by the estimated standard deviations (i.e., standard errors) of the ACS estimates, are used. These estimates are assumed to be unbiased and normally distributed. The latter assumption fails in small samples, the implications of which are considered.

2. The Median Absolute Standardized Error

The Median Absolute Standardized Error (MASE) can be computed using the centered 50% confidence interval of the standard normal distribution. Through computation or lookup, one can find that this confidence interval is $[-.6745, .6745]$. Therefore, half of absolute standardized errors lie above $.6745$ and half below.

3. The Expected Absolute Standardized Error

The Expected Absolute Standardized Error (EASE) is simply the first absolute moment of the standard normal distribution:

$$\text{EASE} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |x| e^{-\frac{z^2}{2}} dz = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}}. \quad (1)$$

4. Small Sample Problems

For sample sizes too small for the normal approximation, the t -distribution has to be used. The confidence values for MASE can be obtained from lookup tables or computed in statistical software. The integral in EASE becomes

$$\text{EASE} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |x| \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{\nu+1}{2}\right)}{\sqrt{\pi\nu}\Gamma\left(\frac{\nu}{2}\right)} \left[1 + \frac{x^2}{\nu}\right]^{-(\nu+1)/2} dx = \sqrt{\frac{\nu}{\pi}} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{\nu-1}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\nu}{2}\right)}, \quad (2)$$

where ν is the number of degrees of freedom, equal to the number of observations used to estimate the ACS rate less one.

5. The Expected Absolute Error

The Expected Absolute Error (EAE) is the unstandardized version of EASE. That is, it includes the standard error estimate. It can only be computed observation by observation as a result of the varying standard error estimates. Its general formula is

$$\text{EAE} = \frac{\text{mean deviation}}{\text{standard deviation}} \hat{\sigma}, \quad (3)$$

where the mean deviation and standard deviation are of the distributions of the estimates of estimation errors for the ACS values, normal in large samples and t in small samples. The division by “standard deviation” accounts for the spread of the unstandardized distribution in small samples.

The standard deviation of the standard normal distribution is 1, so that equation (3) simply becomes

$$\text{EAE} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \hat{\sigma}. \quad (4)$$

When the t -distribution must be used, equation (3) takes on a more complicated form:

$$\text{EAE} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \left[\sqrt{\frac{\nu}{2}} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{\nu-1}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{\nu}{2}\right)} \right] \hat{\sigma}, \quad (5)$$

where ν is the same as in equation (2). Asymptotically, as ν converges to infinity, equation (5) converges to equation (4), as expected.

Note that the expressions for EAE do not account for the distribution of $\hat{\sigma}$, which in a complex survey, is not easily derived. Moreover, it is correlated with the distribution of the estimated rate. Thus, EAEs derived herein should be regarded as approximations to the true EAEs.